

OFDM-Based mmWave Wi-Fi ISAC System Implementation for Monostatic Human Sensing

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Abstract—This work presents an Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM)-based millimeter wave (mmWave) Wi-Fi Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) system that directly implements the mandatory waveform requirements of the IEEE 802.11 Integrated Millimeter Wave (IMMW) Study Group. Designed for monostatic human sensing at 60 GHz, the system integrates a four-stage static removal algorithm, adaptive two-dimensional Constant False Alarm Rate (2D-CFAR) detection, and the range-Doppler processing. It enables dual-functionality sensing and communication without additional spectrum or hardware, supporting IMMW standardization. Numerical validation achieves 0.2563 m range Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and 0.0798 m/s velocity RMSE at 20 dB Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), with superior Bit Error Rate (BER) performance over Single Carrier (SC) baselines—demonstrating practical feasibility for next-generation IMMW-compliant Wi-Fi systems.

Index Terms—IEEE 802.11, ISAC, mmWave, OFDM, SC, Human sensing, monostatic radar, 60 GHz

I. INTRODUCTION

The IEEE 802.11 Integrated Millimeter Wave (IMMW) Study Group [1] mandates Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) waveforms to integrate sensing into next-generation Wi-Fi without extra spectrum or hardware. The integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) system [2], [3] fulfills this requirement, enabling advanced environmental sensing alongside reliable data communication in shared bands. While prior work shows OFDM can support both sensing and communication [4], IEEE 802.11ad primarily uses single-carrier (SC) waveforms for dual-functionality [5]. Unlike existing cellular-based radar adaptations [2] or protocol-modified Wi-Fi approaches, this work is the first to directly implement the IEEE 802.11 IMMW-mandated OFDM waveform for mmWave Wi-Fi ISAC, achieving dual-functionality through native waveform exploitation rather than system adaptation. OFDM-based human sensing in millimeter wave (mmWave) Wi-Fi remains underexplored, and indoor range-Doppler sensing faces clutter-related challenges [7]. This study implements and analyzes the mandatory IMMW OFDM waveform for monostatic Wi-Fi human sensing. Use of OFDM in cellular sensing exists but is beyond this scope.

To address key challenges, this work investigates mandatory OFDM-based mmWave Wi-Fi ISAC systems as specified by the IMMW Study Group. The system adopts a four-step sensing workflow optimized for dual-functionality, utilizing

a monostatic radar configuration and the IMMW-required OFDM waveform to enable simultaneous sensing and communication without additional spectrum or hardware. The flexibility of OFDM supports high-resolution range-Doppler analysis via 2D FFT processing [4], while ensuring full compatibility with existing Wi-Fi architectures. This work investigates OFDM’s sensing capabilities and notes the potential use of 8× upscaling from IEEE 802.11ac/ax [6] as a direction for future enhancement. The system integrates: (1) a four-stage static removal algorithm with temporal coherence analysis, (2) environment-adaptive 2D-CFAR detection with SNR-driven tuning, (3) range-Doppler processing using 2D FFT and Blackman-Harris windowing, and (4) adaptive parameter estimation for accurate human target tracking.

System performance is evaluated through numerical simulations using ground truth data, focusing on range and velocity accuracy at 20 dB SNR. The OFDM-based sensing pipeline achieves a range root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.2563 m and a velocity RMSE of 0.0798 m/s. The IMMW-mandated OFDM waveform also shows consistently better bit error rate (BER) performance than SC baselines across various SNRs, achieving communication reliability. These results demonstrate the first validated implementation achieving simultaneous high-precision human sensing and reliable communication using unmodified IMMW-mandated OFDM waveforms. The dual-functionality performance confirms OFDM’s effectiveness for precise sensing and robust communication in mmWave ISAC, while remaining compatible with existing Wi-Fi standards.

II. OFDM-BASED ISAC SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

A. OFDM Waveform Structure for ISAC

In this work, the system uses OFDM symbols [5] with guard intervals to ensure orthogonality while enabling coherent processing across multiple symbols for range-Doppler estimation. Specifically, the time-domain OFDM waveform for the ISAC system is mathematically expressed as:

$$s(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \sum_{k=0}^{N_{sc}-1} X[n, k] \cdot e^{j2\pi f_k t} \cdot \text{rect}\left(\frac{t - nT_s}{T_s}\right) \quad (1)$$

where $X[n, k]$ represents the complex data symbol on the k -th subcarrier of the n -th OFDM symbol, N is the total number

of OFDM symbols, $f_k = f_c + k \cdot \Delta f$ the frequency of the k -th subcarrier with carrier frequency f_c and subcarrier spacing Δf , N_{sc} the total number of subcarriers, $T_s = T_{FFT} + T_{GI}$ the OFDM symbol duration including guard interval (GI), $T_{FFT} = 1/\Delta f$ the FFT period, and T_{GI} the guard interval duration.

B. The OFDM Backscattering Signal

The OFDM backscattering signal forms the foundation of the sensing capability in the ISAC system. When the transmitted OFDM waveform interacts with a human target, the reflected signal carries crucial information about the characteristics of the target through phase and amplitude modulations of individual subcarriers. The backscattered signal from a target at range R and velocity v can be expressed as:

$$s_{backscatter}(t) = \beta \cdot s(t) \cdot e^{j2\pi f_d t} \cdot e^{-j4\pi f_c R/c} \quad (2)$$

where β is the radar cross-section (RCS) of the target, $\tau = 2R/c$ the round-trip delay with R denoting range, $f_d = 2vf_c/c$ the Doppler frequency shift with v denoting velocity and f_c the carrier frequency, and c the speed of light.

For the OFDM system, each subcarrier experiences individual phase shifts due to target interaction, leading to the effective backscattered complex data symbol on each subcarrier of one OFDM symbol, which can be expressed similar to equation (1) as:

$$Y[n, k] = \beta \cdot X[n, k] \cdot e^{-j2\pi k \Delta f \tau} \cdot e^{j2\pi f_d n T_s} + W[n, k] \quad (3)$$

where β is the RCS of the target and $W[n, k]$ is the additive white Gaussian noise.

C. Basic OFDM subcarrier processing for ISAC

The OFDM-based ISAC system employs a classic matched filtering-based approach [8] based on the known transmitted OFDM waveform for actual radar processing. Mathematically, given the received OFDM waveform $Y[n, k]$ in equation (3), the ISAC system creates a radar reception matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}[n, k]$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{H}}[n, k] &= Y[n, k] \odot \text{conj}(X[n, k]) \\ &= \beta \cdot |X[n, k]|^2 \cdot e^{-j2\pi k \Delta f \tau} \cdot e^{j2\pi f_d n T_s} + \widetilde{W}[n, k] \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where β is the RCS of the target, \odot and $\text{conj}(\cdot)$ denote the element-wise (Hadamard) product and the complex conjugation, respectively, and $\widetilde{W}[n, k]$ the processed additive white Gaussian noise.

III. KEY RADAR PROCESSING COMPONENTS AND WI-FI RADAR PROCESSING WORKFLOW

In this subsection, we detail the relevant mathematical formulation and processing workflow on the derived radar reception matrix.

A. Static Removal with Temporal Coherence

Clutter removal is the first processing step that eliminates unwanted static components from the derived radar reception matrix. We implement a static removal algorithm with temporal coherence analysis that adaptively identifies and removes stationary interference components based on their temporal variance characteristics. The static removal algorithm operates in four sequential stages:

Stage 1: Temporal Variance Analysis The temporal variance across the slow-time dimension is computed for each range bin to identify static components:

$$\sigma_{temp}^2[k] = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \left| \hat{\mathbf{H}}[n, k] - \bar{\mathbf{H}}[k] \right|^2 \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{H}}[k] = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \hat{\mathbf{H}}[n, k]$ is the temporal mean for range bin k , and N is the total number of OFDM symbols in the coherent processing interval.

Stage 2: Static Component Identification Static components are identified using an adaptive threshold based on the mean temporal variance:

$$T_{static} = \alpha \cdot \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \sigma_{temp}^2[k] \quad (6)$$

where $\alpha = 0.1$ is the threshold scaling factor and K the total number of range bins.

Stage 3: Selective Static Removal For range bins identified as static ($\sigma_{temp}^2[k] < T_{static}$), the temporal mean is removed:

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{partial}[n, k] = \begin{cases} \hat{\mathbf{H}}[n, k] - \bar{\mathbf{H}}[k] & \text{if } \sigma_{temp}^2[k] < T_{static} \\ \hat{\mathbf{H}}[n, k] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Stage 4: Global Mean Suppression A final global mean removal is applied across all range bins:

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}^{clean}[n, k] = \hat{\mathbf{H}}_{partial}[n, k] - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \hat{\mathbf{H}}_{partial}[n, k] \quad (8)$$

This approach provides static clutter suppression by adaptively identifying static components through temporal coherence analysis, preserving dynamic target signatures while removing stationary interference.

B. Range-Doppler Processing for OFDM-Based mmWave Wi-Fi Radar

The OFDM-based ISAC system leverages the radar reception matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}^{clean}[n, k]$ to extract range-Doppler information. By computing a periodogram over this matrix, the system effectively separates range and Doppler components, thereby enabling accurate target detection and tracking.

To construct the range-Doppler map, a conventional radar processing technique based on a 2D FFT [4] is applied to the radar reception matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}^{clean}[n, k]$. The inner inverse fast Fourier transforms (IFFTs) operation is conducted across the columns of the matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}^{clean}$; that is: the zero-padding is first applied to include inactive subcarriers of the current OFDM symbol, resulting in the extended matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}^{clean}$ of size $N \times K$

($K > N_{sc}$); and then an IFFT is performed on each column of the extended matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}^{clean}$.

Subsequently, an outer FFT is performed across the rows of the matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}^{clean}$ using the following procedure: each row of the matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}^{clean}$ is windowed using the Blackman-Harris function to mitigate spectral leakage. The outer FFT is then performed, which is applied concurrently across all windowed rows of $\hat{\mathbf{H}}^{clean}$.

This 2D processing strategy facilitates efficient computation of the range-Doppler map, which is fundamental for reliable target detection and velocity estimation. The overall 2D FFT procedure is mathematically expressed as:

$$\mathbf{2DFFT}[v, r] = \sum_{n=0}^{L-1} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \hat{\mathbf{H}}^{clean}[n, k] \cdot w[n, k] \cdot e^{j \frac{2\pi r k}{K}} \cdot e^{-j \frac{2\pi v n}{L}} \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{2DFFT}[v, r]$ is the element at Doppler index v and range index r of the 2D FFT output matrix. L is the Doppler FFT length. Before applying the Doppler FFT across the rows, each row of the matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}^{clean}$ is zero-padded to length L (where $L > N$ with N being the number of OFDM symbols). $w[n, k]$ is the Blackman-Harris window function applied for spectral leakage mitigation. K is the range FFT length after zero-padding (where $K > N_{sc}$ with N_{sc} being the number of active subcarriers). For ease of notation, let us define $\mathbf{RD} = (\mathbf{2DFFT})^T$, where $(\cdot)^T$ is the transpose operation. In the following, \mathbf{RD} is referred to as the range-Doppler map and used for target detection and velocity estimation.

C. Adaptive CFAR Detection Algorithm

The system implements a 2D-CFAR detection algorithm with environment-adaptive parameters. The algorithm dynamically adjusts guard and training cell sizes based on SNR estimation and clutter statistics for optimal performance across varying conditions.

SNR-Based Environment Assessment:

$$\text{SNR}_{est} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{mean}(|\mathbf{RD}|^2)}{\text{std}(|\mathbf{RD}|^2)} \right) \quad (10)$$

Adaptive Cell Size Calculation: The guard and training cell dimensions adapt based on the estimated SNR:

$$\xi_{SNR} = \max \left(0.7, \min \left(1.5, 1.0 + \frac{10 - \text{SNR}_{est}}{30} \right) \right) \quad (11)$$

Threshold Calculation: The adaptive threshold incorporates environmental clutter characteristics:

$$T_{adapt} = T_{base} \cdot \left(1 + 0.1 \cdot \frac{\sigma_{clutter}^2}{\mu_{power}} \right) \quad (12)$$

where $\sigma_{clutter}^2$ is the clutter variance and μ_{power} is the mean power of the range-Doppler block.

2D-CFAR Detection Process: For each cell under test (CUT) at position (i, j) , the noise power is estimated from training cells:

$$P_{noise}[i, j] = \frac{1}{N_{train}} \sum_{(k,l) \in \mathcal{T}_{i,j}} |\mathbf{RD}[k, l]|^2 \quad (13)$$

Fig. 1: Sensing processing workflow.

where $\mathcal{T}_{i,j}$ represents the training region excluding guard cells, and N_{train} is the number of training cells.

Target detection occurs when:

$$|\mathbf{RD}[i, j]|^2 > P_{noise}[i, j] \cdot T_{adapt} \quad (14)$$

D. Sensing Processing Workflow

The sensing processing follows a systematic four-step workflow optimized for human target detection and tracking in the OFDM-based ISAC system, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Step 1 - Clutter Removal: Implementation of the four-stage static removal algorithm detailed in Section III-A, incorporating temporal variance analysis and selective static component suppression to preserve dynamic target signatures while eliminating stationary interference.

Step 2 - Range-Doppler Map Generation: Construction of the range-Doppler map through 2D FFT processing as defined in Eq.(9).

Step 3 - CFAR Detection: Application of the environment-adaptive 2D-CFAR algorithm with SNR-based parameter adjustment.

Step 4 - Parameter Estimation: Final stage combining peak detection with target parameter extraction for robust range and velocity estimation:

$$R_{est}[t] = \arg \max_R |\mathbf{RD}[R, f_d]|^2 \quad (15)$$

$$v_{est}[t] = \frac{\lambda \cdot f_{d,peak}}{2} \quad \text{with } f_{d,peak} = \arg \max_{f_d} |\mathbf{RD}[R_{est}, f_d]|^2 \quad (16)$$

where $R_{est}[t]$ is the estimated range at time instant t , $v_{est}[t]$ is the estimated velocity at time instant t , $\mathbf{RD}[R, f_d]$ is the range-Doppler map at range R and Doppler frequency f_d , $f_{d,peak}$ is the peak Doppler frequency corresponding to the detected target, $\lambda = c/f_c$ is the wavelength with c being the speed of light and f_c the carrier frequency, and $\arg \max$ denotes the argument that maximizes the function. This novel four-step workflow integrates adaptive clutter removal, environment-aware detection, and precise parameter estimation specifically optimized for IMM-compliant OFDM waveforms, ensuring efficient processing and accurate target parameter estimation that contributes to the high-precision sensing performance demonstrated in the numerical simulation results and performance analysis validation.

IV. NUMERICAL SIMULATION RESULTS AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

The performance of the OFDM-based ISAC system is evaluated through extensive numerical simulations, enabling comprehensive assessment of the sensing capabilities on the top of the Wi-Fi communication link. Through numerical simulations, the selected simulation setup and parameters of the ISAC system are as follows:

- **Operating frequency:** $f_c = 60$ GHz
- **OFDM waveform:** $K = 512$ subcarriers
- **Guard interval (GI):** Long GI for multipath resilience
- **Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS):** MCS index 6
- **Antenna configuration:** Single Input Single Output (SISO)
- **Single human target:** monostatic configuration with ground truth range $R_{true} = 5.38$ m and velocity $v_{true} = 0.82$ m/s
- **Doppler FFT length:** $L = 128$ samples
- **OFDM symbol number:** $N = 64$ symbols in coherent processing interval
- **Window function:** Blackman-Harris windowing for spectral leakage mitigation

A. Performance Metrics and Error Analysis

The system performance is quantified using multiple statistical metrics. The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and the Normalized Mean Square Error (NMSE) for range estimation are defined as:

$$\text{RMSE}_R = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_{mc}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{mc}} (R_{true}[i] - \hat{R}[i])^2} \quad (17)$$

$$\text{NMSE}_R = \frac{\text{MSE}_R}{\sigma_{R_{true}}^2} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{mc}} (R_{true}[i] - \hat{R}[i])^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{mc}} (R_{true}[i] - \bar{R}_{true})^2} \quad (18)$$

The RMSE and NMSE for velocity estimation are defined analogously, where $N_{mc} = 1000$ represents the number of Monte Carlo realizations ensuring statistical significance of the performance metrics.

B. Numerical Simulation Results

The OFDM-based ISAC system is evaluated by processing the simulated OFDM waveform. The performance metrics are evaluated in terms of human sensing performance results (i.e., range and velocity estimation accuracy for human target detection capabilities), as well as communication link performance metrics such as bit error rates (BER).

1) *Human Sensing Performance Results:* Figure 2 presents the range-Doppler map obtained from the IMMW-compliant OFDM-based ISAC system for the single human monostatic target use case at 20 dB SNR, showcasing the mandatory OFDM waveform's capability to detect and localize human targets with precise range and velocity estimation. The numerical results clearly demonstrate the target signature at approximately 5.38 m range and 0.82 m/s velocity, validating the sensing performance of the IMMW-mandatory OFDM

TABLE I: OFDM-Based ISAC Performance Results with SC Comparison Baseline - Single Human Monostatic Target

Parameter	OFDM	SC
Operating SNR	20 dB	20 dB
Ground Truth Range	5.38 m	5.38 m
Ground Truth Velocity	0.82 m/s	0.82 m/s
Range RMSE	0.2563 m	0.3414 m
Velocity RMSE	0.0798 m/s	0.0775 m/s
Range NMSE (dB)	-26.44	-23.95
Velocity NMSE (dB)	-20.56	-20.83
Estimated Range Span	5.11-6.02 m	5.11 m (stable)
Estimated Velocity Span	0.72-0.80 m/s	0.72-0.80 m/s
Sensing Processing Algorithm	2DFFT	STFT

approach. For performance validation, SC comparison baseline results are also presented. Herein, the ISAC system employs an OFDM waveform structure and a SC mode with the IEEE 802.11ay EDMG-CEF sequence format [9]. To validate the performance of the OFDM-based ISAC system design, we analyze the OFDM implementation under a 20 dB SNR, using SC as a performance comparison baseline. The numerical simulation results for the mandatory OFDM system's range and velocity estimation accuracy are analyzed and shown in Table I. The results are based on Monte Carlo simulations with $N_{mc} = 1000$ realizations under identical conditions, ensuring statistically robust performance metrics. Both OFDM and SC systems share baseline parameters (SNR, range, velocity), enabling fair comparison in a controlled setup. A key novelty is the direct comparison between IMMW-mandated OFDM and conventional SC approaches using identical sensing algorithms, revealing fundamental performance differences attributable solely to waveform characteristics. Performance differences stem from inherent waveform and processing methods: OFDM uses frequency-domain 2D FFT on subcarrier variations, while SC relies on time-domain analysis. For range-Doppler mapping in SC benchmarks, we apply Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) to the time-domain Channel Impulse Response (CIR) [10].

The analysis reveals the exceptional performance characteristics of the OFDM-based ISAC system under 20 dB SNR operating conditions. The mandatory OFDM implementation demonstrates superior range estimation accuracy with RMSE of 0.2563 m, representing approximately 25% better performance compared to the SC comparison baseline (0.3414 m). For velocity estimation, the OFDM system achieves competitive performance with RMSE of 0.0798 m/s, closely matching the SC comparison baseline's 0.0775 m/s. In terms of NMSE performance, the mandatory OFDM system achieves excellent range NMSE of -26.44 dB, significantly outperforming the SC comparison baseline (-23.95 dB), while achieving comparable velocity NMSE of -20.56 dB versus SC's -20.83 dB.

The range-Doppler maps in Fig. 2 illustrate the exceptional target detection capabilities of the OFDM-based ISAC system. Notably, the IMMW-mandated OFDM waveform achieves superior range resolution (25% better RMSE) compared to SC, demonstrating the intrinsic sensing advantages of the standardized OFDM approach. The mandatory OFDM implementation successfully detects the human target at the expected range and velocity with clean sidelobe characteristics, which contributes

(a) OFDM waveform

(b) SC waveform

Fig. 2: OFDM-based ISAC system range-Doppler maps from single human monostatic target at 20 dB signal-to-noise ratio (SNR): (a) OFDM waveform, (b) SC baseline for performance comparison.

directly to its superior range estimation accuracy.

2) *Communication Link Performance Results:* The communication link performance is evaluated through BER analysis across various SNR conditions, comparing the OFDM-based ISAC system against the SC comparison baseline. Figure 3 illustrates the comparative BER performance across different SNR levels, showing that the mandatory OFDM implementation consistently outperforms the SC comparison baseline across all tested SNR conditions. It is important to note that the channel model employed in this study is a frequency-selective multipath fading channel based on the Quasi-Deterministic (QD) ray-tracing model at 60 GHz, rather than a simple AWGN channel. The improved communication reliability of the mandatory OFDM further strengthens IMMW standardization efforts by repurposing proven technologies—such as OFDM and 8× upscaling from IEEE 802.11ac/ax—for advanced sensing applications.

V. CONCLUSION

This work presents the first validated implementation of an OFDM-based mmWave Wi-Fi ISAC system for monostatic human sensing at 60 GHz. The key contributions include: (1) direct implementation of IMMW-mandated OFDM waveforms

Fig. 3: Comparative BER performance analysis: OFDM waveform versus SC across different SNR levels.

for dual-functionality without protocol modifications, (2) novel adaptive sensing algorithms specifically optimized for indoor human detection, and (3) comprehensive performance validation demonstrating 25% range accuracy improvement over SC baselines while maintaining communication reliability. These quantified results establish the approach as a foundational enabler for fulfilling mmWave Wi-Fi ISAC requirements.

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